

U.S. PASSPORT RENEWAL APPLICATION FOR ELIGIBLE INDIVIDUALS
PLEASE DETACH AND RETAIN THIS INSTRUCTION SHEET FOR YOUR RECORDS

Mailing Date of Application: _____

CAN I USE THIS FORM?

Complete the checklist to determine your eligibility to use this form

- | | | | | |
|---|--------------------------|-----|--------------------------|----|
| I can submit my most recent U.S. passport book and/or U.S. passport card with this application. | <input type="checkbox"/> | Yes | <input type="checkbox"/> | No |
| I was at least 16 years old when my most recent U.S. passport book and/or passport card was issued. | <input type="checkbox"/> | Yes | <input type="checkbox"/> | No |
| I was issued my most recent U.S. passport book and/or passport card less than 15 years ago. | <input type="checkbox"/> | Yes | <input type="checkbox"/> | No |
| The U.S. passport book and/or U.S. passport card that I am renewing has not been mutilated, damaged, lost, stolen or subsequently found. | <input type="checkbox"/> | Yes | <input type="checkbox"/> | No |
| My U.S. passport has not been limited from the normal ten year validity period due to passport damage/mutilation, multiple passport thefts/losses, or non-compliance with 22 C.F.R. 51.41. (Please refer to the back pages of your U.S. passport book for endorsement information). | <input type="checkbox"/> | Yes | <input type="checkbox"/> | No |
| I use the same name as on my most recent U.S. passport book and/or U.S. passport card. --OR-- | <input type="checkbox"/> | Yes | <input type="checkbox"/> | No |
| I have had my name changed by marriage or court order and can submit proper certified documentation to reflect my name change. | <input type="checkbox"/> | Yes | <input type="checkbox"/> | No |

**If you answered NO to any of the statements above,
STOP - You cannot use this form!**

You must apply on application form DS-11 by making a personal appearance before an acceptance agent authorized to accept passport applications. Visit travel.state.gov to find your nearest acceptance facility.

U.S. passports, either in book or card format, are only issued to U.S. Citizens or non-citizen U.S. nationals. Each person must obtain his or her own U.S. passport book or passport card. The passport card is a U.S. passport issued in card format. Like the traditional U.S. passport book, it reflects the bearer's origin, identity, and nationality, and is subject to existing passport laws and regulations. Unlike the U.S. passport book, the U.S. passport card is valid only for entry at land border crossings and sea ports of entry when traveling from Canada, Mexico, the Caribbean, and Bermuda. The U.S. passport card is not valid for international air travel.

PLEASE NOTE: Your new passport will have a different passport number than your previous passport.

FOR INFORMATION AND QUESTIONS

Visit the Department of State website at travel.state.gov or contact the National Passport Information Center (NPIC) toll-free at 1-877-487-2778 (TDD: 1-888-874-7793) or by email at NPIC@state.gov. Customer Service Representatives are available Monday-Friday 8:00a.m.-10:00p.m. and Saturday 10:00a.m.-3:00p.m. Eastern Time (excluding federal holidays). Automated information is available 24 hours a day, 7 days a week.

FAILURE TO PROVIDE INFORMATION REQUESTED ON THIS FORM, INCLUDING YOUR SOCIAL SECURITY NUMBER, MAY RESULT IN SIGNIFICANT PROCESSING DELAYS AND/OR THE DENIAL OF YOUR APPLICATION

NOTICE TO APPLICANTS RESIDING ABROAD

United States citizens residing outside the U.S. or Canada **CANNOT** submit this form to domestic addresses listed on the Instruction Page 2. Such applicants should visit www.usembassy.gov to find the nearest U.S. Embassy or Consulate for procedures for applying outside the United States.

WARNING: False statements made knowingly and willfully in passport applications, including affidavits or other documents submitted to support this application, are punishable by fine and/or imprisonment under U.S. law, including the provisions of 18 U.S.C. 1001, 18 U.S.C. 1542, and/or 18 U.S.C. 1621. Alteration or mutilation of a passport issued pursuant to this application is punishable by fine and/or imprisonment under the provisions of 18 U.S.C. 1543. The use of a passport in violation of the restrictions contained therein or of the passport regulations is punishable by fine and/or imprisonment under 18 U.S.C. 1544. All statements and documents are subject to verification.

See page 2 of the instructions for detailed information on the completion and submission of this form.

WHAT DO I SEND WITH THIS APPLICATION FORM?

- Your most recent U.S. passport book and/or card;
- A certified copy of your marriage certificate or court order if your name has changed;
- Fees; and
- A recent, color photograph.

See below for more detailed information

1. YOUR MOST RECENTLY ISSUED U.S. PASSPORT (BOOK AND/OR CARD FORMAT).

- Submit your **most recently issued** U.S. passport book and/or card. When submitting a U.S. passport book and/or card with this form, please verify that the document was issued at age 16 or older in your current name (or see item #2 below) and issued within the past 15 years. You are also eligible to use this form if you currently have a U.S. passport book and/or card that complies with the previously listed criteria, and would like to obtain an alternative product (U.S. passport book and/or card) for the first time. However, you must submit the product you currently have (U.S. passport book and/or card) with this application. If your U.S. passport book and/or card has been lost, stolen, damaged, or mutilated, you must apply on the DS-11 application form as specified below.

2. A CERTIFIED MARRIAGE CERTIFICATE OR COURT ORDER (PHOTOCOPIES ARE NOT ACCEPTED).

- If the name you are currently using differs from the name on your most recent U.S. passport, you must submit a certified copy of your marriage certificate or court order showing the change of name. All documents will be returned to you by mail. If you are unable to document your name change in this manner, you must apply on the DS-11 application form by making a personal appearance at (1) a passport agency; (2) U.S. embassy or consulate, if abroad; (3) any federal or state court of record or any probate court accepting passport applications; (4) a designated municipal or county official; or (5) a post office, which has been selected to accept passport applications.

3. THE CURRENT PASSPORT FEE (DO NOT SEND ACCEPTANCE AGENT FEE WITH THIS FORM).

- Enclose the fee in the form of a personal check or money order. **MAKE CHECKS PAYABLE TO "U.S. DEPARTMENT OF STATE." THE FULL NAME AND DATE OF BIRTH OF THE APPLICANT MUST BE TYPED OR PRINTED ON THE FRONT OF THE CHECK. DO NOT SEND CASH** Passport Services cannot be responsible for cash sent through the mail. By law, the fees are non-refundable. Please visit our website at travel.state.gov for detailed information regarding current fees. Newly issued passport cards are delivered via first class mail only.

OVERNIGHT DELIVERY SERVICE is only available for passport book (and not passport card) mailings in the United States. Please include the appropriate fee with your application.

FOR FASTER PROCESSING, you may request expedited service. Please include the expedited fee with your application. **Please write "Expedite" on the outer envelope when mailing. Also, TO ENSURE MINIMAL PROCESSING TIME for expedited applications, Passport Services recommends using overnight delivery when submitting the application AND including the appropriate postage fee for return overnight delivery for the newly issued passport book.** Expedited service is only available for passports mailed in the United States and Canada. Please visit travel.state.gov for updated information regarding fees, processing times, or to check the status of your passport application online.

4. A RECENT, COLOR PHOTOGRAPH.

- Submit a color photograph of you alone, sufficiently recent to be a good likeness of you (**taken within the last six months**), and 2x2 inches in size. The image size measured from the bottom of your chin to the top of your head (including hair) should not be less than 1 inch, and not more than 1 3/8 inches. The photograph must be in color, clear, with a full front view of your face. The photograph must be taken with a neutral facial expression (preferred) or a natural smile, and with both eyes open and be printed on photo quality paper with a plain light (white or off-white) background. The photograph must be taken in normal street attire, without a hat, or head covering unless a signed statement is submitted by the applicant verifying that the hat or head covering is part of recognized, traditional religious attire that is customarily or required to be worn continuously when in public or a signed doctor's statement is submitted verifying the item is used daily for medical purposes. Headphones, "bluetooth", or similar devices must not be worn in the passport photograph. Glasses or other eyewear are not acceptable unless you provide a signed statement from a doctor explaining why you cannot remove them due to medical reasons (e.g., during the recovery period from eye surgery). Any photograph retouched so that your appearance is changed is unacceptable. A snapshot, most vending machine prints, hand-held self portraits, and magazine or full-length photographs are unacceptable. A digital photo must meet the previously stated qualifications, and will be accepted for use at the discretion of Passport Services. Visit our website at travel.state.gov for details and information.

USE CAUTION WHEN STAPLING YOUR PHOTO: Use 4 staples vertically in the corners as close to the outer edge as possible. Do not bend photo.

WHERE DO I MAIL THIS APPLICATION?

FOR ROUTINE SERVICE (If you live in CA, FL, IL, MN, NY, or TX):
National Passport Processing Center
P.O. Box 640155
Irving, TX 75064-0155

FOR ROUTINE SERVICE (If you live in any other state or Canada):
National Passport Processing Center
P.O. Box 90155
Philadelphia, PA 19190-0155

FOR EXPEDITED SERVICE (Additional Fee, any state or Canada):
National Passport Processing Center
P.O. Box 90955
Philadelphia, PA 19190-0955

Because of the sensitivity of the enclosed documents, Passport Services recommends using trackable mailing service when submitting your application.

NOTE REGARDING MAILING ADDRESSES: Passport Services does not send mail to a private address outside the United States or Canada. If you do not live at the address listed in the "Mailing Address", then you must put the name of the person and mark it as "In Care Of." If your mailing address changes prior to receipt of your new passport, please contact the National Passport Information Center (NPIC) at 1-877-487-2778 or visit travel.state.gov.

You may receive your newly issued document and your returned citizenship evidence in separate mailings. If you are applying for both a passport book and/or card, you may receive **three separate mailings**: one with your returned citizenship evidence; one with your newly issued passport book, and one with your newly printed passport card.

If you choose to provide your email address in Item #6 on this application, Passport Services may use that address to contact you in the event there is a problem with your application or if you need to provide additional information to us.

FEDERAL TAX LAW

Section 6039E of the Internal Revenue Code (26 USC 6039E) and 22 U.S.C. 2714a(f) require you to provide your Social Security number (SSN), if you have one, when you apply for or renew a U.S. passport. If you have never been issued a SSN, enter zeros in box #5 of this form. If you are residing abroad, you must also provide the name of the foreign country in which you are residing. The U.S. Department of State must provide your SSN and foreign residence information to the U.S. Department of Treasury. If you fail to provide the information, you are subject to a \$500 penalty enforced by the IRS. All questions on this matter should be directed to the nearest IRS office.

NOTICE TO CUSTOMERS APPLYING OUTSIDE A DEPARTMENT OF STATE FACILITY

If you send us a check, it will be converted into an electronic funds transfer (EFT). This means we will copy your check and use the account information on it to electronically debit your account for the amount of the check. The debit from your account will usually occur within 24 hours and will be shown on your regular account statement.

You will not receive your original check back. We will destroy your original check, but we will keep the copy of it. If the EFT cannot be processed for technical reasons, you authorize us to process the copy in place of your original check. If the EFT cannot be completed because of insufficient funds, we may try to make the transfer up to two times, and we will charge you a one-time fee of \$25, which we will also collect by EFT.

FEE REMITTANCE

Passport service fees are established by law and regulation (see 22 U.S.C. 214, 22 C.F.R. 22.1, and 22 C.F.R. 51.50-56), and are collected at the time you apply for the passport service. If the Department fails to receive full payment of the applicable fees because, for example, your check is returned for any reason or you dispute a passport fee charge to your credit card, the U.S. Department of State will take action to collect the delinquent fees from you under 22 C.F.R. Part 34, and the Federal Claims Collection Standards (see 31 C.F.R. Parts 900-904). In accordance with the Debt Collection Improvement Act (Pub.L. 104-134), if the fees remain unpaid after 180 days and no repayment arrangements have been made, the Department will refer the debt to the U.S. Department of Treasury for collection. Debt collection procedures used by the U.S. Department of Treasury may include referral of the debt to private collection agencies, reporting of the debt to credit bureaus, garnishment of private wages and administrative offset of the debt by reducing, or withholding eligible federal payments (e.g., tax refunds, social security payments, federal retirement, etc.) by the amount of your debt, including any interest penalties or other costs incurred. In addition, non-payment of passport fees may result in the invalidation of your U.S. passport book and/or card. An invalidated passport book or card cannot be used for travel.

USE OF SOCIAL SECURITY NUMBER

Your Social Security number will be provided to the U.S. Department of Treasury, used in connection with debt collection and checked against lists of persons ineligible or potentially ineligible to receive a U.S. passport book and/or card, among other authorized uses.

NOTICE TO APPLICANTS FOR OFFICIAL, DIPLOMATIC, OR NO-FEE PASSPORTS

You may use this application if you meet all of the provisions listed on Instruction Page 2; however, you must CONSULT YOUR SPONSORING AGENCY FOR INSTRUCTIONS ON PROPER ROUTING PROCEDURES BEFORE FORWARDING THIS APPLICATION. Your completed passport will be released to your sponsoring agency for forwarding to you.

IMPORTANT NOTICE TO APPLICANTS WHO HAVE LOST OR HAD A PREVIOUS U.S. PASSPORT BOOK AND/OR PASSPORT CARD STOLEN

A United States citizen may not normally bear more than one valid or potentially valid U.S. passport book or more than one valid or potentially valid U.S. passport card at a time. Therefore, when a valid or potentially valid U.S. passport book or U.S. passport card cannot be presented with a new application, it is necessary to submit a Form DS-64, Statement Regarding a Lost or Stolen U.S. Passport. Your statement must detail why the previous U.S. passport book or U.S. passport card cannot be presented.

The information you provide regarding your lost or stolen U.S. passport book or passport card will be placed into our Consular Lost or Stolen Passport System. This system is designed to prevent the misuse of your lost or stolen U.S. passport book or passport card. Anyone using the passport book or passport card reported as lost or stolen may be detained upon entry into the United States. Should you locate the U.S. passport book or passport card reported lost or stolen at a later time, report it as found, and submit it for cancellation. It has been invalidated You may not use that passport book or passport card for travel.

PROTECT YOURSELF AGAINST IDENTITY THEFT! REPORT YOUR LOST OR STOLEN U.S. PASSPORT BOOK OR PASSPORT CARD!

For more information or to report your lost or stolen U.S. passport book or passport card by phone, call NPIC at:

1-877-487-2778 or visit our website at travel.state.gov

NOTICE TO U.S. PASSPORT CARD APPLICANTS ONLY

The maximum number of letters provided for your given name (first and middle) on the U.S. passport card is 24 characters. The 24 characters may be shortened due to printing restrictions. If both your given names are more than 24 characters, you must shorten one of your given names on item 1 of this form.

ACTS OR CONDITIONS

(If any of the below-mentioned acts or conditions have been performed by or apply to the applicant, the portion which applies should be lined out, and a supplementary explanatory statement under oath (or affirmation) by the applicant should be attached and made a part of this application.)

I have not, since acquiring United States citizenship/nationality, been naturalized as a citizen of a foreign state; taken an oath or made an affirmation or other formal declaration of allegiance to a foreign state; entered or served in the armed forces of a foreign state; accepted or performed the duties of any office, post, or employment under the government of a foreign state or political subdivision thereof; made a formal renunciation of nationality either in the United States, or before a diplomatic or consular officer of the United States in a foreign state; or been convicted by a court or court martial of competent jurisdiction of committing any act of treason against, or attempting by force to overthrow, or bearing arms against the United States, or conspiring to overthrow, put down, or to destroy by force, the government of the United States.

Furthermore, I have not been convicted of a federal or state drug offense or convicted of a "sex tourism" crime, and I am not the subject of an outstanding federal, state, or local warrant of arrest for a felony; a criminal court order forbidding my departure from the United States; or a subpoena received from the United States in a matter involving federal prosecution for, or grand jury investigation of, a felony.

PRIVACY ACT STATEMENT

AUTHORITIES: Collection of this information is authorized by 22 U.S.C. 211a et seq.; 8 U.S.C. 1104; 26 U.S.C. 6039E, 22 U.S.C. 2714a(f), Section 236 of the Admiral James W. Nance and Meg Donovan Foreign Relations Authorization Act, Fiscal Years 2000 and 2001; Executive Order 11295 (August 5, 1966); and 22 C.F.R. parts 50 and 51.

PURPOSE: We are requesting this information in order to determine your eligibility to be issued a U.S. passport. Your Social Security number is used to verify your identity.

ROUTINE USES: Your Social Security number will be provided to the Department of the Treasury and may be used in connection with debt collection, among other purposes authorized and generally described in this section. This information may be disclosed to another domestic government agency, a private contractor, a foreign government agency, or to a private person or private employer in accordance with certain approved routine uses. These routine uses include, but are not limited to, law enforcement activities, employment verification, fraud prevention, border security, counterterrorism, litigation activities, and activities that meet the Secretary of State's responsibility to protect U.S. citizens and non-citizen nationals abroad. More information on the Routine Uses for the system can be found in System of Records Notices State-05, Overseas Citizen Services Records and State-26, Passport Records.

DISCLOSURE: Providing information on this form is voluntary. Be advised, however, that failure to provide the information requested on this form may cause delays in processing your U.S. passport application and/or could also result in the refusal or denial of your application.

Failure to provide your Social Security number may result in the denial of your application (consistent with 22 U.S.C. 2714a(f)) and may subject you to penalty enforced by the Internal Revenue Service, as described in the Federal Tax Law section of the instructions to this form.

ELECTRONIC PASSPORT STATEMENT

The U.S. Department of State now issues a type of passport book containing an embedded electronic chip called an "Electronic Passport". The electronic passport book continues to be proof of the bearer's United States citizenship/nationality and identity, and looks and functions in the same way as a passport without a chip. The addition of an electronic chip in the back cover enables the passport book to carry a duplicate electronic copy of all information from the data page. The electronic passport book is usable at all ports-of-entry, including those that do not yet have electronic chip readers.

Use of the electronic format provides the traveler the additional security protections inherent in chip technology. Moreover, when used at ports-of-entry equipped with electronic chip readers, the electronic passport book provides for faster clearance through some of the port-of-entry processes.

The electronic passport book does not require special handling or treatment, but like previous versions should be protected from extreme heat, bending, and from immersion in water. The electronic chip must be read using specially formatted readers, which protects the data on the chip from unauthorized reading.

The cover of the electronic passport book is printed with a special symbol representing the embedded chip. The symbol will appear in port-of-entry areas where the electronic passport book can be read.

PAPERWORK REDUCTION ACT STATEMENT

Public reporting burden for this collection of information is estimated to average 40 minutes per response, including the time required for searching existing data sources, gathering the necessary data, providing the information and/or documentation required, and reviewing the final collection. You do not have to supply this information unless this collection displays a currently valid OMB control number. If you have comments on the accuracy of this burden estimate and/or recommendations for reducing it, please send them to: Passport Forms Officer, U.S. Department of State, CA/PPT/S/L, 44132 Mercure Cir, P.O. Box 1227 Sterling, Virginia 20166-1227.

Name of Applicant (Last, First & Middle) Date of Birth (mm/dd/yyyy)

12. Height 13. Hair Color 14. Eye Color 15. Occupation 16. Employer or School (if applicable)

17. Additional Contact Phone Numbers

Home Cell Work Home Cell Work

18. Permanent Address: If P.O. Box is listed under Mailing Address **or** if residence is different from Mailing Address.

Street/RFD # or URB (No P.O. Box) Apartment/Unit

City State Zip Code

19. Emergency Contact - Provide the information of a person not traveling with you to be contacted in the event of an emergency.

Name Address: Street/RFD # or P.O. Box Apartment/Unit

City State Zip Code Phone Number Relationship

20. Travel Plans

Departure Date (mm/dd/yyyy) Return Date (mm/dd/yyyy) Countries to be visited

**STOP! YOU HAVE COMPLETED YOUR APPLICATION
BE SURE TO SIGN AND DATE PAGE ONE**

WHERE DO I MAIL THIS APPLICATION?

If applying in the United States or Canada:

FOR ROUTINE SERVICE (If you live in CA, FL, IL, MN, NY, or TX):
National Passport Processing Center
P.O. Box 640155
Irving, TX 75064-0155

FOR ROUTINE SERVICE (If you live in any other state or Canada):
National Passport Processing Center
P.O. Box 90155
Philadelphia, PA 19190-0155

FOR EXPEDITED SERVICE (Additional Fee, any state or Canada):
National Passport Processing Center
P.O. Box 90955
Philadelphia, PA 19190-0955

Because of the sensitivity of the enclosed documents, Passport Services recommends using trackable mailing service when submitting your application.

If applying outside the United States or Canada:

United States citizens residing outside the U.S. or Canada **CANNOT** submit this form to domestic addresses listed above. Such applicants should visit www.usembassy.gov to find the nearest U.S. Embassy or Consulate for procedures for applying outside the United States.

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